

OBSERVATION AND QUANTIFICATION OF DAMAGE EVOLUTION IN CROSSPLY CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES AT LOW TEMPERATURE USING DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

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ABSTRACT

The investigation of low temperature fracture in high and low temperature cured cross ply, unidirectional, carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites using digital image correlation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Unidirectional (UD) prepreg carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) possess superior in plane properties to woven systems. They offer large weight saving in structural, weight critical sectors such as aerospace. UD prepregs are inherently anisotropic possessing high longitudinal strengths and relatively poor transverse strengths. As a result UD prepreg systems are often laminated into cross ply laminates to manage out of plane loading. However, UD systems also possess widely differing longitudinal (fibre dominated) and transverse (matrix dominated) linear coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). With approximate longitudinal and transverse CTE of $-0.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ and $30 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ respectively [1]. Consequently, cross ply UD laminates with fibres in a 0° and 90° orientation result in CTE mismatch between plies [2]. When combined with the low transverse strengths, thermal loading alone can induce transverse failure [2]. Whilst transverse cracks may not significantly impact on the overall mechanical properties they can act as stress concentrators, providing a pathway to freeze thaw cracking from moisture ingress.

It is well known that the degree of cure of an epoxy system is related to the fracture toughness [3]. The aim of this paper is to investigate the fracture resistance of high and low temperature cure schedule UD CFRP cross ply laminates from 60°C to -80°C . Adams *et al* [2] tested a range of UD CFRP cross ply laminates; those with high levels of 90° plies on the outside of a panel such as $[90_3, 0]_s$ cause transverse cracking in the central ply. To ensure low temperature fracture the worst case scenario panel of $[90_3, 0]_s$ will be investigated.

Digital image correlation utilises the changes sequential images of a textured surface during deformation to produce a surface strain field. This enables visualisation of crack formation. Mostafavi and Marrow used digital image correlation to measure the crack length and opening

displacement profile at different loading conditions [4]. To visualise crack generation during cooling of samples, in situ DIC will be utilised.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

400 x 400 mm [90₃, 0]_s laminates were produced using 660 gsm HR40 UD MTM46 prepreg supplied by Cytec Ltd. Laminates were laid up on a 770NC Frekote (Henkel, Germany) mould released aluminium sheet. Debulking was performed every 4 plies for 15 minutes at room temperature (20°C) to aid consolidation. Samples were then cured under vacuum using the following two cure schedules designated low temperature cure (LTC) and high temperature cure (HTC):

Table 1 Low and high temperature cure cycles

Low temperature cure	High temperature cure
Ramp at 2°C/min to 80°C	Ramp at 2°C/min to 135°C
80°C Dwell for 300mins	135°C Dwell for 90mins
Ramp at 2°C/min to 20°C	Ramp at 0.3°C/min to 180°C
Ramp at 2°C/min to 80°C	180°C Dwell for 60mins
Ramp at 0.3°C/min to 120°C	Ramp at 3°C/min to 20°C
120°C Dwell for 120mins	
Ramp at 3°C/min to 20°C	

Degree of cure was determined using a Perkin and Elmer DSC8500 differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Samples of uncured prepreg and LTC and HTC panels were sectioned using a diamond saw and powdered using a cryomill (Retsch, Germany). This was done to normalise the fibre volume fraction and average out sections of the panel. Samples of 5 – 10 mg were sealed in aluminium pans and ramped to 250 °C at 100 °C/min and isothermally held for 30 minutes until the samples had fully cured. The energy of residual cure was taken from the levelling of the reaction where all reactants were used up and the system was fully cured. The peak area of curing was calculated using Perkin and Elmer Pyris software giving the energy per gram of material. The degree of cure was calculated using:

$$\% Cure = \frac{(\Delta H_{Uncured} - \Delta H_{Thermallycycled})}{\Delta H_{Uncured}} \times 100 \quad [5]$$

Where $\Delta H_{Uncured}$ is the energy of reaction Joule per gram of the uncured prepreg, whilst $\Delta H_{Thermallycycled}$ is the energy of reaction of the LTC and HTC samples.

Two 40mm squares were cut from each panel then polished along the cut face such that the centre ply was orientated with the fibres running transverse to the polished face as shown in Figure 1. This was done to visualise transverse cracking of the central ply and to ensure the surface was level for the camera. Samples were polished using 1200 grit carbide paper proceeded by a 9 and 6µ diamond suspension polish. A speckle pattern was applied to the polished sample face using an air brush with water soluble paints. A thin white base coat was applied before a black speckle being applied to the sample.

Figure 1 Side view of polished panels and cameras field of view

The DIC setup is shown in Figure 2. A Imager E-lite 5M camera 5 Mega pixel camera with 2.45 K x 2 K pixel resolution and a pixel size of $3.45 \times 3.45 \mu\text{m}$ with LED lamps from Lavison ltd were spaced along a tripod. The camera was levelled and aligned to the samples surface using a circular spirit level and rulers. Samples were supported in the environmental chambers field of view using a matt black painted aluminium block to reduce reflections. A Tokina AT-X Pro D 100mm F2.8 macro lens was set to an aperture of f8 to maximize focus whilst maintaining a workable focal length. Calibration was performed using a glass calibration plate with a grid of 0.25 mm dots supplied by Lavison. Post calibration, samples were placed back into the field of view until the speckle appeared focused. From here the samples were taped to the block using a low temperature tape to prevent the sample moving during the introduction of Liquid nitrogen (LN_2). A K-type thermocouple was taped to the upper surface of the sample to enable sample temperature logging. The thermocouple was converted into a voltage readout using a SMCJ thermocouple to analogue converter from Omega Ltd. The temperature voltage readout was added as an analogue input into Lavison enabling sequential temperature logging with image capture. Recording of images and temperature were set to 0.5 Hz. Samples were then dwelled at 60°C for 10 minutes to homogenize the sample temperature. The chamber temperature was then set to -100°C and LN_2 cooling, temperature logging and image capture commenced.

Figure 2 Set of DIC equipment

DIC was used to determine the surface displacements and crack formation and propagation. In order to carry out such analysis, the LA Vision Davis software was used (Version 8.2.3).

Shift correction and intensity normalisation was used to remove sample shift due to aluminium sample holder contractions, sample and camera vibration. The normalisation accounted for the intensity decrease due to fogging and frosting of the chamber window. A 256 pixel area for shift correction was placed centrally at the top of the image allowing subpixel level shifts. The centre top was chosen due to low deformation for each sample.

Image correlation was performed using the least squares matching method. A rectangular mask was inset from the edges of the sample to avoid edge effects. In all cases the sample eventually fractured through the centre of the image producing a discontinuity in the image, consequently two seeding points at the top and bottom of the sample were utilised. A subset size and step size of 55 and 20 pixels were used respectively.

The resulting displacement field was exported and using a custom Matlab script, crack detection and horizontal average crack opening was determined. The code automatically detects the discontinuity in the displacement field and uses the vectors outside of the discontinuous region to detect the crack opening displacement. The crack opening displacement was calculated by subtracting the displacement vector from each subset displacements on opposite sides of the crack. This was then averaged across the crack for each image.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DSC results demonstrate a degree of cure of 77.7 % for LTC and 93.1% for HTC samples for a 250 °C cured system as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Degree of cure of low and high temperature cure MTM46 panels

Sample	Degree of cure (%)
Low temperature cure	77.7
High temperature cure	93.1

DIC calibration was tested over the experimental range of temperatures to investigate any variations in the window and experimental setup. The calibration process was repeated at 40 degrees intervals and the standard deviation of the process varied roughly around 0.3 pixels. The pixel to mm conversion factor at this temperature range was 284.7 ± 1.697 pixel/mm. This can be interpreted as a displacement measurement accuracy of 1 μ m for calibration and 6 μ m for temperature change.

Figure 3 and Figure 4 show high and low temperature cured speckled samples respectively as they are cooled from 60°C to -80°C. The coloured vector field demonstrates the samples principal strain and is optimized for each image (see scale bar). From Figure 3 it is clear that in both of the high temperature cured samples have transverse cracked by the time they reached 20°C and crack propagation between transverse cracks has initiated. By -60°C both panels have large scale delamination across the central ply.

The low temperature cured systems as shown in Figure 4 demonstrate lower level of transverse cracking at 20°C. As the cooling progresses to -60°C the samples demonstrated a buildup of transverse cracks. As cooling progresses below -60°C the cracks start to join up causing central ply failure.

Figure 3 Principal strain (scaled per image) of high temperature cured panels cross sections as the samples are thermally loaded.

Figure 4 Principal strain (scaled per image) of low temperature cured panels cross sections as the samples are thermally loaded.

Figure 5 demonstrates the resulting horizontal crack opening displacement versus temperature as determined using the custom MATLAB script. This was plotted against sample temperature. The HTC samples demonstrated onset of fracture at -17.6 °C and -36.7 °C (taken from visualisation of horizontal crack formation) and the LTC samples had onset of fracture at -53.2 °C and -68.0 °C.

Figure 5 Crack opening displacement of horizontal cracks versus loading temperature of low and high temperature cured [90₃, 0]s MTM46 HR40 panels.

4 CONCLUSIONS

MTM46 cross ply laminates cured at 120 °C (LTC) and 180 °C (HTC) have a degree of cure of 77.7% and 93.1% respectively. The LTC system demonstrated greater resistance to temperature induced fracture than the HTC sample. The MATLAB script was demonstrated as an effect method for determination of crack opening displacement. Fracture occurred at -17.6 °C and -36.7 °C for HTC samples whilst LTC samples fractured at -53.2 °C and -68.0 °C. Sample HTC 2 didn't show an obvious crack opening, in order to draw a clear conclusion, more samples will be tested and will be presented in a further publication. Cure temperature has a marked effect on residual stress and the temperature at which temperature induced internal fracture occurs. This data is important in optimising cure schedule for carbon epoxy laminates exposed to low temperatures in aerospace applications.

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